

“DESIGN AND FABRICATION OF AUTOMATIC DRAINAGE CLEANING MACHINE USING IOT”

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Abstract— In urban areas, maintaining clean and functional drainage systems is crucial for preventing flooding and ensuring public health. Traditional manual cleaning methods are often inefficient and costly. This paper presents an innovative solution leveraging IoT (Internet of Things) and GPS (Global Positioning System) technologies to automate the cleaning process of drainage systems. The proposed system consists of several components including smart sensors placed within the machine to monitor the level of debris. GPS modules to track the location of cleaning machine and a centralized control system for data processing and decision-making. By automating the drainage cleaning process, this system reduces the reliance on manual labour, minimizes the risk of human error, and improves the overall effectiveness of drainage maintenance efforts. Additionally, the integration of IoT and GPS technologies enables proactive maintenance scheduling based on predictive analytics, further enhancing the system's efficiency and cost-effectiveness. This research contributes to the advancement of smart city infrastructure by offering a scalable and sustainable solution for drainage system management, ultimately promoting environmental sustainability, and improving the quality of life for urban residents.

Keywords— Smart city infrastructure, GPS, IoT (Internet of Things)

1. INTRODUCTION

The Automatic drainage cleaning system utilizing IoT technology, Now-a-days even though automation plays a vital role in all industrial applications in the proper disposal of sewages from industries and commercials are still a challenging task. Automatic Drainage Water Cleaning overcomes all sorts of drainage problems and promotes blockage free drains promoting continuous flow of drain water. In the modern era there have been adequate sewage problems where sewage water needs to be segregated to clean our surrounding environment.

Our proposed system is used to clean and control the drainage level using auto mechanism technique. Water running through a water drainage system mostly carries along waste materials most which are

nonbiodegradable which not only cause flooding but also climate change. Overflow of water drainage system occurs when there is a blockage of an end of the drainage system forcing the water to find its way elsewhere apart from the mapped-out drainage system, therefore the running water spills over the horizontal height of the drainage systems spreading to regions alongside the drainage system, thereby causing problems such as pushing down of structures such as fences, water logging of farm lands and residential building, etc. The impurities present in water can cause hazardous and disease. As long as the draining system is considered the function of the main drainage system is to collect, transport and dispose of the water through an outfall or outlet. Impurities in drainage water can be only like empty bottles, polythene bags, papers, etc. The problem such as Environmental pollution and spreading of viral diseases are avoidable. Automation of Drainage Cleaning System would reduce the risk of various diseases spread due to accumulation of waste. This Drainage Cleaning system will clean the waste at the surface of drainage which would allow the flow of water. The devices is place across drain so that only water flow through lower grids, waste like bottle, etc. Floating in drain are lifted by teeth which is connected to chain. This chain is attached by gear driven by motor. When motor runs the chain starts to circulate making teeth to lift up. The waste materials are lifted by teeth and are stored in waste storage tank.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Ganesh U L, et.al. [1] Design and Fabrication of semi-automatic drainage cleaning system Showed the usage of mechanical drainage cleaner to replace the manual work required for drainage cleaning system. Drainage pipes are very dirty. Sometimes it is harmful for human life while it is need for cleaning drainage system. To overcome this problem, they implemented mechanical semiautomatic drainage water cleaner and so the water flow is efficient because of regular filtration of wastages with the help of that project. Different kinds of environment hazards reduced with the help of Drainage system machine.

From this project, it is concluded that our project is helpful for separating solid waste from the drainage water which will further avoid the blockage of drainage line and avoiding flooding. • Separation of these solid waste helps in treating the solid waste and thus converting it into degradable waste. • Being light in weight this kind of system can be placed at the junction points of the drainage system that are frequently subjected to blockages.

Researchers Kavin Bharathi E , Mohankumar D , Rajesh Kanna P. ME[2] Fabrication of Drainage Cleaning Machine This project is made with pre planning, that it provides flexibility in operation. Smoother and noiseless operation by the medium This project “FABRICATION OF DRAINAGE CLEANING MACHINE” is designed with the hope that it is very much economical and help full to many apartments, hotels and houses. This project helped us to know the periodic steps in completing a project work. Thus we have completed the project successfully.

Dr. k.kumaresan [3] explained manual work converted to automated system. Drainage pipe using for disposal, and it may be loss for human life while cleaning the blockage in the drainage pipes. To overcome this problem they implemented “Automatic Sewage Cleaning System”. This project may be developed with the full utilization of men, machines, and materials and money. They made their project economical and efficient with the available resources. They used automation technology related with his application of mechanical, electronics, computer based systems to operate and control production. [3]

Balachandra et al. [4] “Fabrication of Drainage Cleaning Machine,”

Reviewed about drainage cleaning to replace manual work to automated system because manually cleaning system it is harmful for human life and cleaning time, is more so to overcome this problem they implemented a design “Automatic drainage water pump monitoring and control system using PLC and SCADA”. PLC and SCADA were designed. In this project to use efficient way to control the disposal of wastage regularly, treatment of disposal in different way toxic and nontoxic gases. PLC controller from Siemens was used in the treatment system of drainage wastewater control by the stepper motor, compressor, gas exhauster, pressure valve and the liquid level, flow and other analog variables to achieve automatic control of sewage waste water treatment. [4]

3. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for intended work is being planned to be carried out as per the flowchart given below. First carrying out study of the available source of material and understanding the method drainage cleaning machine. Then the design of drainage cleaning machine and its fabrication is done, later the testing of drainage cleaning is carried out.

Fig .1 flow diagram of project

Parts Specification

Battery:

Fig.2 Battery Circuit

Sealed Rechargeable battery.
AB 12V 7.2/12V-7.2 AH

Voltage Parameters
Constant Voltage Charge (27°C)
Cycle use: 14.1 V- 14.4 V Max. Current; 1.4 A

<p>Application: Universal low power IoT sensor hub. Home automation. Universal low power IoT recorder. Wireless control. OTT TV box / set-top box device. Sensor networks.</p>	<p>Features: Integrated 520 KB RAM. Hybrid Wi-Fi & Bluetooth. High level of integration. On-board PCB antenna.</p>
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Table: Application and Features

DC Motor

These motors open a wide choice for you in terms of wheels and chassis, specifications -,

Rpm - 30,

shaft diameter - 6mm (with internal hole).

weight - 125gms,

torque - 8 kg/cm.

voltage - 6 to 24 (nominal voltage - 12v).

no-load current = 60 ma (max).

load current = 300 ma (max).

Gear ratio Calculation.

Fig 3:- Driven gear

Driven gear diameter = 21mm

Driven pitch circle diameter= 11mm

Number of Driven gear teeth= 8

$$\text{Gear ratio} = \frac{\text{number of Driven gear teeth}}{\text{number of Driver gear teeth}} = \frac{8}{28} = \frac{2}{7}$$

This is written as 2:7

Fig 4:- driver gear

Driver gear diameter = 56mm

Driver pitch circle diameter = 52

Number of driver gear teeth = 28

Collecting Bin, Shaft, Mesh Plate

Fig 3.1: Collecting Bin
 Length of the bin = 360mm
 Width of the bin = 250mm
 Height of the bin = 200mm
 Volume of the bin =
 $L*W*H = 360*250*200 = 18000000 \text{ mm}^3$

Fig 3.2: Shaft
 Length of the shaft = 450 mm
 Diameter of the shaft = 15 mm
 Volume of the shaft = $\pi r^2 h = 3.14 * 450 * 7.5$
 $= 79521.56 \text{ mm}^3$

Fig 3.3: Mesh Plate

Length of the plate = 640mm

Breadth of the plate = 350mm

Area of the rectangular plate = length * breadth = 640 * 350 = 224000 mm²

Model Dimensions:

Length of the model = 720mm

Width of the model = 400mm

Height of the model = 750mm

- Load carrying capacity of the model = 500gm in 19.04 sec
1000gm in 17.10 sec
1500gm in 17.59 sec
- Speed of the machine = 1 complete cycle in 38.36 sec
- How much torque is produced by motor = 25 n/m
- Collecting bin carrying capacity = 3kg

4.EXPERIMENT WORK

Single lifter load v/s time

In Automatic drainage cleaning system different loads are added on single lifter and time taken was tabulated in below table.

Weight (in gm)	Time (in sec)
1500	19
2000	19.5
3000	21.4

Multi-lifter Load distribution v/s time

In Automatic drainage cleaning system different loads are added on multi- lifter and time taken was tabulated in below table.

Weight (in gm)	Time (in sec)
1500	17.59
2000	20.96
3000	21.54

Different weight v/s time

In Automatic drainage cleaning system different loads are added and time taken was tabulated in below table.

Weight (in gm)	Time (in sec)
200	15
300	16.77
500	19.04
1000	20.36

Conduction of different material

In Automatic drainage cleaning system different materials are added and time taken was tabulated in below table.

Material	Time (in sec)
plastic bottle	13.5
thermocool	10.4
wood	20.7
plant west	8

5. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Single lifter load v/s time

In Automatic drainage cleaning system different loads are added on single lifter and time taken was shown in below graph.

Multi-lifter Load distribution v/s time

In Automatic drainage cleaning system different loads are added on multi- lifter and time taken was shown in below graph.

Different weight v/s time

In Automatic drainage cleaning system different loads are added and time taken was shown in below graph.

Conduction of different material

In Automatic drainage cleaning system different material are added and time taken was shown in below graph.

6. CONCLUSION

Automation is a technology concerned with the application of mechanical, electronic and computer-based systems to operate and control production. This system is used to operate automatic drainage cleaning system. This project may be developed with the full utilization of men, machines, materials and money. Also, we have followed thoroughly the study of time motion and made our project economical and efficient with the available resources.

- The maximum load carrying capacity of the model is 5.5kg to 7kg.
- The experiment conducted indicate that, the average time for the single lifter to lift 2.16 kg weight comes out to be 19.96 s.
- The experiment conducted indicate that, the average time for the multi-lifter to lift 2.16 kg weight comes out to be 20.03 s.
- The experiment conducted indicate that, the average time for the different weight to lift 2 kg weight comes out to be 17.79 s.
- The ultrasonic sensor identifies the filling of bucket at different levels like 75%,100%. Once it reaches it sends a push notification to a mobile app that bin is full
- In this system GPS enables real-time tracking of the cleaning system's location, allowing operators to monitor its movement along the drainage network. This helps in ensuring comprehensive coverage of the drainage system and optimizing cleaning routes for efficiency.

7. REFERENCES

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